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PRODUCTIVE WORD FORMATION AND BORROWING PATTERNS IN ARABIC

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Abstract: This article investigates the key productive models of word formation and borrowing used to enrich the lexical composition of the Arabic language, with a particular focus on the formation of internet terminology. It analyzes the internal mechanisms of the language, such as the morpho-root method and semantic transformation, as well as external factors like calquing and transliteration. The article also touches upon the sociolinguistic phenomenon of Arabizi.

Keywords: Arabic language, word formation, borrowings, terminology, internet terms, morpho-root method, semantic transformation, calquing, transliteration, Arabizi.

INTRODUCTION

The Arabic language, as a living and evolving system, constantly expands its lexical composition to adequately reflect the changing realities of the world. In the context of rapid scientific and technological progress and globalization, especially in the field of information technologies, the process of forming new terminology becomes extremely intensive and requires a comprehensive approach to studying productive models of word formation and borrowing. Terminology is the most dynamic and rapidly updated part of the language, contributing to the global penetration of new meanings and concepts into various spheres of activity.

The aim of this article is to analyze the main productive models of word formation used in the Arabic language to create new vocabulary, and to examine the mechanisms of borrowing that play a significant role in enriching its terminological system, particularly in the domain of internet terminology.

MAIN PART

Stages of Development of the Arabic Terminological System. The history of Arabic terminology is a multi-century process that can be divided into five main stages:

1. Internal Resources of the Arabic Language: Productive Word Formation Models. The Arabic language possesses a high internal linguistic potential for forming new vocabulary, including internet terms. This is due to its root-affix structure, the flexibility of its word-formation models, and extensive affixes.

1.1. Morpho-Root Method. The morpho-root method is the most productive in the Arabic language, accounting for approximately 40% of the analyzed material in the context of internet terminology. This method is based on derivative verbal forms and allows for the creation of terms without resorting to external borrowings. Among the most productive models are:

Active Participle (اسم الفاعل *ism al-fā'il*): Formed from verbs and indicates the doer of an action. Examples in the internet context: مُدَوِّن (*muddawwin*) – «blogger» (from «to blog»), مُحَمِّل (*muhammil*) – «uploader» (from «to upload»).

Passive Participle (اسم المفعول *ism al-maf'ul*): Indicates the object upon which an action is performed. Examples: مُرْسَل (*mursal*) – «sent» (file, document), مُسَجَّل (*musajjal*) – «registered», مَحْظُور (*maḥzūr*) – «blocked».

Abstract Nouns with the suffix -ية (-iyyah): Formed from nouns or adjectives, denoting abstract concepts. Examples: معلومانية (*ma'lūmātiyyah*) – «informatics» (from معلومات *ma'lūmāt* – «information»), خصوصية (*khuṣūṣiyyah*) – «confidentiality, privacy» (from خصوص *khuṣūṣ* – «privacy»), افتراضية (*iftirāḍiyyah*) – «virtuality» (from افتراضي *iftirāḍī* – «virtual»).

Noun of Instrument (اسم الآلة *ism al-ālāh*): Models denoting tools or techniques. Examples: حاسوب (*ḥāsūb*) – «computer» (from حسب *ḥasaba* – «to calculate»), مُرَشِّح (*murashshih*) – «filter, spam filter» (from رشح *rashshaḥa* – «to filter, to purify»). In the internet context, these are used in combinations such as مُرَشِّح البريد المزعج (*murashshih al-barīd al-muz'aj*) – «spam filter» or مُرَشِّح المحتوى (*murashshih al-muḥtawā*) – «content filter».

Models مِفْعَل (*mif'al*), مِفْعَلَة (*mif'alah*), مِفْعَال (*mif'āl*), مِفْعَالَة (*mif'ālah*): These models ensure systematic formation of specialized vocabulary for the virtual space. For example: مِخْزَن (*mikhzan*) – «storage» (*mif'al*), مِحْفَظَة (*miḥfazah*) – «wallet» (*mif'alah*), مِفْتَاح (*miḥfazah*) – «key» (*mif'āl*), مِرْسَالَة (*mirsālah*) – «messaging system» (*mif'ālah*).

Masdars (Verbal Nouns) (المصدر *al-maṣḍar*): Name an action. Examples: تَحْمِيل (*tahmīl*) – «download», تَعْلِيق (*ta'līq*) – «comment», مِشَارَكَة (*mushārakah*) – «share», إِعْجَاب (*i'jāb*) – «like».

The high frequency of these models is due to their universality and structural flexibility, which ensures the organic integration of new terms into the syntactic and semantic system of the Arabic language without losing its morphological integrity.

1.2. Semantic Transformation. Semantic derivation and the active use of existing lexical material allow the Arabic language to productively create new terms

(accounting for approximately 20% of the analyzed material). This demonstrates the language's high adaptive capacity and includes:

Terminologization of a common word's meaning. The transformation of a general meaning into a specialized one. For example, حقل (*ḥaql*) – «field» (a plot of land) acquires the meaning of «information field» (حقل المعلومات *ḥaql al-ma'lūmāt*) in the internet segment.

Extension of a common word's meaning: Giving a word a broader meaning to encompass new concepts. For example, شبكة (*shabakah*) – «net» (originally a fishing net), now – الشبكة العالمية (*al-shabakah al-ālamīyah*) – «worldwide web».

Metaphorization of meaning. Using a word in a figurative sense, often based on analogies. For example, موجة (*mawjah*) – «wave» (sea wave), but in internet terminology, it can mean «wave of cyberattacks» (موجة من الهجمات الإلكترونية *mawjah min al-hujumāt al-iliktirūniyyah*).

Narrowing of a common word's meaning. Creating a term by restricting the meaning of a word within a specific domain. For example, عملية (*amaliyyah*) – «operation» (various actions), but in internet terminology – «specific software intervention», as in عملية التجديد (*amaliyyah al-tajdīd*) – «update process».

2. External Factors: Mechanisms of Borrowing. External sources of terminology enrichment play an important, yet complementary, role in relation to internal models.

2.1. Calquing is one of the effective and systematic ways to replenish internet terminology in the Arabic language (approximately 20% of the studied terms). This process allows for the preservation of the conceptual content of the borrowed term while adapting it to the norms of the Arabic language and ensuring a high level of comprehensibility for native speakers. Types of calquing include:

Full Calquing (morphological correspondence). Each element of the source word or expression is translated separately. For example, شبكة اجتماعية (*shabaka ijtimā'iyyah*) – «social network» (English «Social network»), محرك بحث (*muḥarrrik baḥth*) – «search engine» (English «Search engine»).

Partial Calquing (semantic correspondence). Only one of the elements of the term is borrowed, while the second is replaced by an Arabic equivalent. For example, بريد إلكتروني (*barīd iliktrūnī*) – «electronic mail» (English «Electronic mail»).

Semantic Calquing (extension of an existing word's meaning). Not the word itself is borrowed, but its scientific and technical meaning, while preserving the structure and morphology of the Arabic word. For example, نافذة (*nāfidhah*) – «window» (graphical interface window), by analogy with English «Window».

2.2. Transliteration is one of the main methods of borrowing foreign terms into Arabic internet terminology (approximately 10% of the studied terms). It is primarily used to convey technical and specialized terms of the virtual space that

have no direct equivalents in Arabic. Examples: ويب(*wib*) – Web, إيميل(*īmayl*) – e-mail, فيسبوك(*fiysbūk*) – Facebook, إنترنت(*intirnet*) – Internet, هاكر(*hakkir*) – hacker, فايروس(*fayrus*) – virus. The Arabic language adapts English words to its phonetics and writing system. Some sounds absent in the Arabic alphabet (e.g., [p] and [v]) are replaced by phonetically similar letters.

2.3. Arabizi is a hybrid language, a stable form of informal written communication, representing a combination of the Latin alphabet, numeric characters, and Arabic phonemes. It emerged as a result of technical limitations of early internet infrastructure but gained the status of an independent sociolinguistic phenomenon. Arabizi facilitates the rapid adaptation of borrowed internet vocabulary into everyday virtual use, accelerating its integration as internet terms (comprising approximately 10% of the studied internet terminology).

CONCLUSION

The Arabic language demonstrates a high adaptive capacity in forming new vocabulary, especially in the context of the rapid development of internet communications. Productive word formation models, based on the language's internal resources such as the morpho-root method and semantic transformation, enable it to autonomously create a significant volume of terminology. At the same time, external mechanisms, such as calquing and transliteration, play an important role in integrating international vocabulary. The phenomenon of Arabizi highlights the flexibility of the Arabic language and its adaptation to informal forms of digital communication.

Understanding and systematizing these productive models of word formation and borrowing are crucial for the further standardization of Arabic terminology and ensuring its effective functioning in the global information space.

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